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D12.1 Final interim report on Virtual Access

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Abbreviations

AHA	Active and Healthy Aging
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CAD	Computer Aided Design
CC BY	Creative Commons with attribution (BY)
CC BY-NC	Creative Commons with attribution (BY) and Non-Commercial
CSV	Comma Separated Value
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DP	Discovery Portal
EC	European Commission
EHDS	European Health Data Space
eHLQ	Electronic Health Literacy Questionnaire
EU	European Union
ER	External Researcher, same as VA participant
ETL	Extract, Transform, Load

FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
ID	Identifier
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISCED	International Standard Classification of Education
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JSON Linked Data
JRA	Joint Research Activities
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MAUQ	Measuring the Acceptance and Usefulness of Multimedia Applications
NDM	Non-VITALISE Data Model compliant
NLP	Natural Language Processing
LL	Living Lab
ODbL	Open Database License
PII	personally identifiable information
PPDL	Public Domain Dedication and License
PDF	Portable Document Format
QUIS	Questionnaire for User Interaction Satisfaction
REST	Representational State Transfer
RGB	Red Green Blue
RAI	Research Analysis Identifier
RDF	Resource Description Framework

SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol
SUMI	Software Usability Measurement Inventory
SUS	System Usability Scale
SQL	Structured Query Language
TA	Transnational Access
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
VA	Virtual Access
VDMC	VITALISE Data Model Compliant
WP	Work Package
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

Executive summary

The document provides a comprehensive overview of the Virtual Access (VA) experience within the VITALISE project, detailing the design, methodology, and execution phases. It outlines the cataloguing of datasets for open science community publication, emphasizing compliance with regulatory frameworks and proper licensing for dataset exploitation. Two main dataset categories, their advantages, and disadvantages are discussed. The VA experiment plan is delineated, identifying and classifying variables for analysis.

Quantitative and qualitative metrics, including questionnaires inspired by existing tools like the System Usability Scale (SUS), are specified to assess VA participant experiences. The execution phase involves continuous activities like monitoring user registration and technical issues to ensure smooth operation. Upon data collection, the analysis phase begins to produce the final VA report.

Key considerations include data valuation, where relevant criteria such as information relevance, availability, and licensing are evaluated. Transformation costs, privacy, and legal compliance, particularly regarding GDPR regulations, are also emphasized. Various data sources are explored, from file tables to semantic formats, with an emphasis on data interoperability and standardization.

The document highlights the importance of comprehensive, diverse, and readily available datasets for external researchers. It underscores the need for robust collaboration and feedback mechanisms between data providers and researchers to enhance dataset archiving and foster innovation. Overall, the success of VA activities hinges on data quality, accessibility, and adherence to legal and privacy standards.

Through a proper planning, execution, and analysis, the VITALISE project aims to facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration, drive innovation, and advance research efforts across various domains.

1 Introduction

1.1 The VITALISE Project

Researchers in the Health and Wellbeing domain need 1) convenient access to research infrastructures, 2) direct engagement of people in order to validate hypotheses, co-design solutions and services, evaluate their feasibility and effectiveness and participate in the translation and mobilization of outcomes and 3) experience from multidisciplinary domains (e.g. healthcare management, assistive technologies, data science) to deal with the complexity of health and wellbeing research.

Over the last few years, Living Labs have emerged as resilient research and innovation infrastructures and have proved to be key to the integration of research and innovation processes in real life settings, focusing primarily on people and their engagement in research procedures. VITALISE opens up Living Lab Infrastructures as a means to facilitate and promote research activities in the Health and Wellbeing domain in Europe and beyond by enabling in person Transnational Access to 17 Living Lab research infrastructures and by supporting remote digital access to datasets (Virtual Access) of rehabilitation, transitional care and everyday life activities through harmonized processes and common tools. VITALISE designs and develops ICT tools for shared access of similar devices and applications used across Living Labs, as well as for collecting, storing and sharing datasets. Lastly, VITALISE invests in the development of Training methods towards the wider understanding and valorisation of Living Lab methodologies in the research community.

1.2 Description of WP12

In Work Package 12 (WP12) of the VITALISE Project, our focus lies on facilitating seamless access to the datasets collected during the Joint Research Activities (JRAs) and Transnational Access (TAs). Our mission is not only to grant access to them but also to ensure the secure management of Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) and the acknowledgment of researchers' contributions, respecting regulations for personal and sensitive data.

Our primary objective is to enable researchers to explore and utilize the diverse datasets generated within the project, by establishing clear access policies, allowing for flexible data sharing while upholding security and privacy standards.

Through the development of access policies based on permissions or licenses, we seek to promote open data and open science principles. Security measures are integrated throughout all levels, from infrastructure to data and access, ensuring compliance with data protection regulations such as GDPR and HIPAA.

Virtual Access will be granted to researchers who applied, without any selection criteria.. Subsequent submission of analysis summaries and publications allows us to monitor the quality of work and assess the effectiveness of Virtual Access.

WP12 relies on the outcomes of WP5, WP6, and WP7 (i.e. the Joint Research Activities); as well as WP8, WP9 and WP10 (i.e. the Transnational Access), which generate the datasets accessed through Virtual Access. WP3 also supports Virtual Access by providing the technological infrastructure and platform to provide Virtual Access to datasets, by generating synthetic data as well as safely running digital experiments over the data. The other work packages of the VITALISE project also support WP12 in their different capacities.

In essence, Work Package 12 serves as the gateway to a pool of data generated with the VITALISE project, enabling researchers to access and use them for research in the health and wellbeing domain, while safeguarding the integrity and security of valuable information. This experience will not only provide proof of the value of the research generated by the project, but it will also prove as a viable service for future exploitation of the research infrastructures. To this end, Living Labs will be able to support their Research Infrastructures' operations by safely sharing data, engaging in open

science approaches and promoting the living lab models for experimental research to the science community at large and the health and wellbeing communities in particular.

1.2.1 Applicable KPIs

There are Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined which the VITALISE project strides to accomplish. Some of the defined KPIs provide important context to WP12, and the decisions explained in this document:

1. **KPI1.2: Number of Total Researchers Recruited for Virtual Access:** In order to attract researchers the offered VA dataset catalogue needs to contain a high number of datasets.
2. **KPI2.1: Different Types of Datasets:** Diversifying the range of datasets available within the VITALISE platform encourages researchers to register and perform more and better research.
3. **KPI2.2: Qualitative Measures of Researcher Satisfaction with Datasets:** The satisfaction of researchers engaging in Virtual Access activities needs to be collected, the comprehensive feedback mechanisms and satisfaction surveys, we gather qualitative data on researchers' experiences with the datasets.
4. **KPI5.2: Satisfaction of Researchers to Process Data Online Rather Than Download and Process the Datasets on Their Computers:** The Discovery Portal's feature to run experiments on Datasets, eliminates the need for cumbersome downloads, local processing; and adds secure anonymity feature to the datasets.
5. **KPI6.1: Willingness of Researchers to Share Their Data for Processing Through the VITALISE Platform:** On the data producers' side, VA needs to engage data owners to share their data, by enabling safe and easy platform to do so.

All these KPIs are pivotal in the development of WP12 activities and its outcomes. Thus, they are something the reader should consider when reading this deliverable, as they are driving many of the decisions and priorities.

1.3 About this deliverable

This report is planned to include the reports produced by the researchers that participated in VA activities. Since there was no obligations from the researchers to report back to the consortium the results produced after the VA, this deliverable focuses on the reports provided by the researchers at the registration phase.

Since we believe it is important to describe the tools, methodologies, activities, and decisions within WP12 enabling the coordination of VA across multiple work packages in the project, we are reporting these actions in this final interim report on Virtual Access. This allows us to report in detail all the background information needed to enable VA, as well as all the activities previous, and during VA along with the registration reports of Participants.

The internal results and analyses (such as statistics on the access provided to researchers) and external results and analyses (such as the optional final reports and publications produced by the researchers participating in VA) will be reported in D12.2, being this second deliverable the pure results aspect of the VA.

The structure of this deliverable is as follows: Section 2 contains a methodological approach to Identification of Datasets for VA, including theoretical considerations and constraints applicable to the decision-making process of identifying candidate datasets and evaluating whether each candidate may be published as part of VA. These considerations and constraints have been essential for dataset curation, 1 on 1 interviews and metric requirements steps. Section 0 offers an insight into the dataset publication process and final catalogue offered to VA participants. This methodology establishes the fundamental types of datasets as specified in the VITALISE platform tools. The iterative process followed to construct the catalogue of datasets is described along with the requirements for enabling VA monitoring and a short summary of the tools used for VA. Section 4 establishes the needed variables for analysis of VA and presents the questionnaire for VA participants to answer. Section 0 contextualizes all the methodologies into the overall VA experiment

plan, explaining in detail the phases, timeline and activities within each in order to execute the VA experience.

Section 6 summarizes the registration reports produced by VA researchers when registering into the platform. This summary provides an insight into the expectations of VA researchers towards VA, and how these expectations are met through the methodological approach provided by the previous sections of the deliverable. The last section, Section 7, offers conclusions structured around the main phases of VA, linking all the methodologies together into a cohesive and executed action plan.

2 Identification of Datasets for Virtual access

As part of the Virtual Access (VA) experience, researchers must be able to access high-quality, relevant datasets in order to be used for research. In this section we explain the methodology used to identify and select the datasets as well as the conditions necessary for publication in the VITALISE platform for the broader research community to access them.

2.1 Dataset curation process

In the context of the VITALISE project, the process of dataset curation that includes the collection and valuation (i.e. finding value in it, not to be confused with evaluation) of datasets from research infrastructures, is crucial. On one side the availability of high number of datasets helps VA participants to engage in the VA experience, as it increases the probability of a VA researcher being interested in VA in general or in a particular dataset. The diversity of datasets is also something that might attract VA researchers as it increases the chances to find a dataset falling into their research interest, as well as providing opportunities where multiple datasets are combined to produce new research interest. Quality is another key factor for VA researchers, as only high-quality datasets can produce research of enough quality to increase the chances of scientific publications.

In this section we propose the usage of a 2-step method to first identify possible existing data in the research infrastructures, and then to select the best fitting datasets through their value.

2.1.1 Data identification

The initial phase involves the identifications of the datasets available within each research infrastructure. Characteristics such as file type (e.g.CSV or Microsoft Excel document), application domain had to be collected in order to come up with a list of potential dataset candidates, as well as their format and some preliminary metadata (simple data descriptions).

2.1.2 Data valuation methodology

Once a comprehensive list of datasets was compiled, this next phase focuses on evaluating the value and relevance of each dataset to the objectives of the VITALISE project. Criteria such as relevance to use cases, representability within the project's data model, availability, volume, quality, potential connection mechanisms, and compliance with privacy and legal regulations were considered. The key considerations in the context of the VITALISE project are listed below:

- **Privacy and Legal Considerations:** Ensuring compliance with privacy regulations such as GDPR and adherence to legal requirements when collecting and processing the data. Data that meets privacy and legal standards and can be securely managed within the VITALISE platform is prioritized.
- **Licensing:** Is the information usable under the terms and conditions of the data agreement? Sometimes datasets in research infrastructures are results of research projects and are collected under strict usage conditions, even economic conditions may apply. Datasets following FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable), and data offered under open and free licenses may be prioritized.
- **Availability:** Confirming the accessibility and availability of the data for integration into the VITALISE Discovery Portal. Check that the data is readily accessible, it can be obtained without significant barriers. It is preferred if the data is continuously updated, for a more valuable integration.
- **Relevance to Use Cases:** Assessing how each dataset contributes to addressing the specific use cases and objectives outlined in the VITALISE project. Datasets that directly support research activities and objectives are prioritized for further processing and integration.
- **Volume of Information:** Considering the size and volume of the dataset in relation to the overall project requirements and objectives. Large datasets may require more resources for processing and integration, whereas smaller datasets may be more manageable.

- **Quality of Information:** Assessing the reliability, accuracy, and consistency of the data. High-quality datasets sourced from reliable sources are prioritized, while datasets with potential errors or inconsistencies may require further validation and pre-processing.
- **Scalability and Sustainability:** Considering the scalability and long-term sustainability of integrating the dataset into the VITALISE Discovery Portal. Datasets that can support future growth and scalability of the project are given preference.
- **Interoperability and Integration Potential:** Assessing the dataset's compatibility with existing systems and technologies within the VITALISE ecosystem. Datasets that can seamlessly integrate with other project components and features (such as synthetic data generation or experiment running) are prioritized.
- **User Feedback and Demand:** Considering feedback from researchers and stakeholders regarding the relevance and usefulness of the dataset. Datasets that align with user requirements and demonstrate demand are prioritized for integration.

At the end of the valuation analysis, the list of the eligible candidate datasets was produced. For each candidate each of the above considerations was explained, and a plan for transformation/integration was provided.

2.2 Anonymization constraints

Anonymization is the process of removing or modifying Personally Identifiable Information (PII) from a dataset in such a way that individuals cannot be re-identified from the remaining data. The goal of anonymization is to protect individuals' privacy while still allowing the dataset to be used for analysis, research, or other purposes.

VITALISE applied all the measures for ensuring individuals' privacy by removing or disguising sensitive personal information, ensuring compliance with data protection regulations such as the GDPR, which mandates the use of anonymization techniques to mitigate privacy risks in data collection, processing, and sharing. Ethical approvals and the usage of the approved informed consents ensured responsible data practices and respecting individuals' privacy rights.

Some anonymization techniques which were used to improve the datasets before VA publication included the **De-identification**: removing direct and indirect identifiers (i.e. any PII) from the dataset to prevent re-identification of individuals. **Pseudonymization**: replacing direct identifiers with pseudonyms or unique identifiers, making it more difficult to identify individuals without additional information. **Synthetic Data Generation**: creating artificial datasets that mimic the statistical properties and patterns of real-world data while ensuring that individual records cannot be linked back to real individuals.

In order to take the maximum measures, VITALISE provided VA access only to anonymized datasets to ensure that all datasets selected are legally compliant and do not impose exceptional measures which might have jeopardized the execution of VA across all infrastructures.

2.3 Licensing requirements

If there is no license specified for a dataset, it is usually considered to be under traditional copyright law. In this case, users have very limited rights to use the dataset, typically only what is allowed under fair use or fair dealing provisions of copyright law. Necessary rights for VA, like that to be redistributed through the Discovery Portal, or creation of derivative works such as synthetic data in RAI nodes are not granted by this default license.

Thus, from WP12 we analysed the common licensing schemes for datasets open enough to enable published datasets to be used in the VA experience, balancing the rights retained by the dataset creator. To simplify the process for dataset creators, we have selected the Creative Commons Licenses¹ license scheme which would work and comply with all of the requirements of VITALISE as a project. For datasets, the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license is commonly used,

¹ <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/>

which allows others to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the dataset, even commercially, as long as they give appropriate credit to the original creator. This license covers important set of requirements imposed by the VA experience, such as redistribution, attribution, remix and use restrictions. Selecting the appropriate license thus demanded careful consideration of these factors to align with the goals and values of the VITALISE project for VA as well as the regulatory landscape. Ultimately, the choice of license depends on the goals of the dataset creator, their preferences regarding how the dataset should be used, and the desired balance between openness and control.

Licenses are applied by clearly specifying the terms and conditions under which the intellectual property, such as datasets, can be used, shared, and modified. The process of applying a license typically involves the license documentation including the terms and conditions of the license, integration of the license information with the dataset itself, typically through metadata or accompanying documentation, distribution and sharing of the licence terms with the dataset, and attribution and compliance with the terms of the license from the users who access or use the dataset. These set of requirements have been negotiated with WP3 for the implementation of dataset upload and retrieval, which is essential for VA experience, when providing access to participants not bounded by the terms of VITALISE contract.

3 Publication of Datasets

This section presents the final catalogue of datasets offered to VA participants along with the description of the datasets publication process. In order to contextualise the actions, it is important to describe the fundamental types of datasets as specified in the VITALISE platform tools as each has a unique set of properties and implications on the publishing process. The publication itself follows an iterative process to construct the catalogue of datasets. First allowing the research infrastructures to propose datasets and then following up with each of them based on a methodological approach. The requirements of the tool were developed according to the required data metrics to be collected through the publishing of datasets as well as the execution of the VA. These requirements were forwarded to the tool development team enabling VA monitoring with all the interesting variables. Although the tools used for VA are developed within WP3, a brief analysis of them is offered from the perspective of VA execution to contextualize the whole VA.

3.1 Dataset Data Models

The VITALISE Platform specifies a data model as part of its main operations. This data model is what data entries need to be compliant, as to be able to benefit from many features the VITALISE system provides. The datasets that are compliant with this data model are referred as VITALISE Data Model Compliant (VDMC) datasets. These datasets benefit from key features such as synthetic data generation (see D3.3), as the algorithms need to operate on the data based on the specified data model. Another feature which depends on data model compliance is the remote experiment execution (see D3.5) as the VA experiment developer needs to know the data model of the data to develop the algorithm which implements the experiment.

Datasets that are not compliant with the VITALISE data model are referred as Non-Data Model compliant (NDM) datasets. These datasets cannot be used by synthetic data generation algorithms, and thus they do not have the benefit of the valuable features the platform offers such as synthetic data generation, or remote experiment execution. On the bright side, NDMs are more flexible as they allow any type of data, from any origin as long as it is convertible into a CSV (comma separated value) file. Consequently, it is more convenient for Living Lab Research Infrastructures to find and provide NDM datasets while the dependencies of VDMC dataset make these type of datasets more complex to produce and maintain.

All of these reasons combined meant that VA activity preparation was highly focused on NDM processing, and most VDMC management was led by WP3.

3.2 Dataset publishing process

Before a dataset is released through the Discovery Portal, specific requirements must be met to comply with regulations and data integrity. These standards serve as guidelines to support transparency, protect privacy, and encourage better use of data. The criteria for publishing a dataset are as follows:

1. The dataset must have permissions for publication from the VITALISE Living Lab Research Infrastructure and must fall within the scope of VITALISE.
2. The dataset must not contain private data, being either anonymized or synthetic. The author must confirm the anonymization status and explicitly accept publication if the data is not anonymized.
3. The dataset must have a valid license.

This approach adheres to the Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) standards, ensuring appropriate description, documentation, and cataloguing of datasets. By conforming to DCAT, it promotes effortless integration with the European Health Data Space (EHDS), thereby enhancing the ability to contribute effectively to the broader objectives of data interoperability and accessibility within the healthcare sector.

3.2.1 First exploration

The initial step was to conduct a screening to identify the datasets available from the VITALISE Living Labs prior to concluding the data collection phase for the implementation of various JRAs small-scale pilots. The following parameters were collected and assessed for each dataset:

- *Identifier*: unique identifier of the dataset if available, like DOI.
- *Category*: JRA1/JRA2/JRA3 or Health/AHA for those that are provided by the Living Labs beyond the JRAs activities.
- *Name*: distinctive name for the dataset.
- *Keywords*: related keywords which help find the dataset.
- *Description*: short description of the dataset to be published in the project website.
- *Creation date*: date of the creation of the dataset (at least the year).
- *Update date*: date of the last edition of the dataset (at least the year).
- *Version*: version of the dataset, if applicable.
- *Creator (institution)*: contact of the person/entity who created the dataset, for asking questions regarding the content and context of the dataset.
- *Dataset owner*: contact of the person/entity to ask for permission to use.
- *Publisher*: the person/entity in charge of the distribution of the dataset.
- *GDPR status/consent*: have the Data owners consent to.
- *Anonymization status*: whether the dataset is anonymized and how.
- *License*: type of license, and which uses does it allow; as well as any other particular condition applicable.
- *Language*: the main language used in the dataset for free text and metadata expressions.
- *Size (#entries)*: total number of entries of the dataset, to provide an idea of the size of the dataset.
- *Type*: format used to encode the dataset (CSV or format that can be easily converted to CSV).
- *Content model*: short summary of the data model used for the dataset, as well as any semantic description of the fields, and their types and possible values.

13 potential collections of datasets falling under the Health or AHA categories were identified (see Table 1), each characterized by unique attributes that underwent analysis for potential inclusion in the dataset collection for Virtual Access operations. However, six of these collections were discarded due to the disagreement on a required license.

Table 1 Description of First Exploration Datasets

ID	Category	Name	Keywords	Description
DOI1 ²	Health	GameBus reinforcement schedules monetary incentives	mHealth, behavior change, gamification, rewards	<p>This dataset stems from a six-week, three-arm randomized intervention trial conducted with university staff members and students (N = 61). The study explores the use of mHealth apps in promoting health behavior change via financial rewards. Researchers assessed the impact of various reinforcement schedules on app engagement levels.</p> <p>This dataset offers valuable insights for researchers aiming to optimize mHealth interventions and encourage healthier behaviors through app design and reward systems.</p>
DS01	AHA	Aging and wellbeing	Aging, elderly, wellbeing	<p>This dataset provides a comprehensive collection of variables related to the quality of life, socio-demographic characteristics, and physical activity of older individuals. It includes data from validated quality of life questionnaires (such as EQ5D3L and UCLA) and offers insights into the well-being and lifestyle of this demographic.</p> <p>This dataset offers a valuable resource for researchers interested in enhancing the understanding of older adults' quality of life, health, and lifestyle choices. It can inform interventions, policy decisions, and healthcare strategies aimed at improving the well-being of this demographic.</p>
DS02	AHA	Older adults and technological innovations	Older adults, technological innovation, qualitative data, user cafe	<p>This dataset presents qualitative data gathered during two user café sessions involving older adults. In each session, participants engaged in discussions about three Nordic innovations. These discussions encompassed questions arising from product introductions, deliberations on the pros and cons of the innovations, and suggestions regarding potential target groups for these innovations.</p> <p>This dataset offers valuable qualitative information for researchers interested in user-centered innovation development and understanding how older adults perceive and engage with novel products and technologies. It can inform product refinement, marketing strategies, and innovation targeting in the Nordic context.</p>

² <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.16692271.v2>

ID	Category	Name	Keywords	Description
	AHA	JRA3 - Setting the path for the future Gradior Active Tool	Older adults (65+), very mild and mild cognitive decline, technology usability, adherence, user experience and suitability	The dataset relates to a shorter testing phase (2 months of weekly sessions), coupled with a co-creation process to identify strengths and areas for improvement of a prototype for physical and cognitive training that combines motion and cognitive activities with independent and unrelated purposes (“Dual Task”). It incorporates controlled physical exercises (aerobic, strength, balance and flexibility exercises) using motion capture technologies (Kinect). The goal of the data collection was not to validate the tool but to revisit and understand this prototype, which is the result of research from over 10 years ago, and assess its potential. This understanding will be crucial in deciding further investments for an upgraded version of the prototype.
DOI2 ³	AHA	Senior balance test	senior, balance, physical functioning, balance board	<p>This dataset involves the utilization of the Standout Balance Board, developed by Smartifier Ltd (https://www.standoutbalance.com/), for balance testing in individuals aged 65 and older. The Standout Balance Board is a standard balance board with a 40cm diameter and 7cm height, equipped with a built-in 3D accelerometer, gyrometer, and magnetometer. It connects to smartphones, tablets, and other devices via Bluetooth. The primary assessment method employed in this study involves a 30-second erect stance on the board with eyes open.</p> <p>This dataset offers valuable information for researchers interested in balance assessment technology and its application in monitoring and improving the balance of older individuals. It can inform further research into fall prevention strategies and the development of personalized balance training programs.</p>

³ <https://doi.org/10.23729/0945fbf3-7a8d-4c69-b76f-5cf6ce92fa94>
 ©VITALISE Consortium <https://vitalise-project.eu>

ID	Category	Name	Keywords	Description
DS04	Health	Captiv motion VR mirror therapy	Captiv angles VR mirror therapy	This dataset includes joint angle measurements of the upper limb, specifically the wrist, elbow, and shoulder joints. These measurements were collected while participants engaged in virtual mirror therapy, a rehabilitative approach commonly used in the early stages of recovery for individuals with hemiplegia. During virtual mirror therapy, participants exercise their healthy side, aiming to promote the reactivation of the affected side. While the dataset primarily focuses on the "healthy side," it can also be employed to monitor the progression of the affected upper limb during rehabilitation. This dataset offers valuable insights for researchers interested in motor rehabilitation, mirror therapy, and upper limb movement analysis in the context of hemiplegia. It can inform the development of targeted rehabilitation strategies and personalized interventions to enhance recovery for individuals with impaired upper limb function.
DS05	Health	COVID-X cough dataset	COVID-19; cough; health	This dataset comprises audio recordings collected during the COVID-X EU project, focusing on monitoring COVID-19 patients with varying symptom severity. A sound recorder was employed to capture all sounds, with a specific threshold for recording applied. The dataset consists of two categories of audio data: 1) Cough Data: Audio recordings of cough sounds from COVID-19 patients and 2) No-Cough Data: Audio recordings capturing sounds other than coughs from the same patients. This dataset serves as a valuable resource for researchers working on audio-based diagnostics and monitoring in the context of COVID-19. It can aid in the development of innovative tools and technologies for remote patient monitoring and early symptom detection.
DS06	Health	MS-NEUROPLAST_H	Patients with Multiple sclerosis, Healthy Controls, Electroencephalography	This dataset comprises EEG (Electroencephalogram) measurements obtained using a 128-channel EEG system. The EEG recordings were conducted both before and after a cognitive training intervention in two groups: patients diagnosed with Multiple Sclerosis (MS) and a group of healthy control participants. The dataset allows for the examination of how cognitive training impacts EEG patterns in these two distinct populations. This dataset offers valuable insights for researchers interested in neurocognitive assessments, the impact of cognitive training on brain activity, and how these effects may differ between individuals with Multiple Sclerosis and healthy controls. It can inform the development of targeted interventions to enhance cognitive function in MS patients.

ID	Category	Name	Keywords	Description
DS07	Health	MS-NEUROPLAST_Ψ	Patients with Multiple sclerosis, Healthy Controls, Neuropsychological evaluation	This dataset includes results from a battery of neuropsychological tests administered to two groups: patients diagnosed with Multiple Sclerosis (MS) and a group of healthy control participants. The tests were conducted both before and after a cognitive training intervention. The dataset allows for the examination of changes in cognitive performance in response to cognitive training in these two distinct populations. This dataset provides valuable information for researchers interested in cognitive assessments, the efficacy of cognitive training interventions, and the cognitive differences between individuals with Multiple Sclerosis and healthy controls. It can aid in the development of tailored cognitive training programs for MS patients to improve cognitive function and quality of life.
DS08	Health	MS-NEUROPLAST_Σ	Patients with Multiple sclerosis, Healthy Controls, Somatometric evaluation	This dataset contains results from a battery of somatic tests administered to two groups: patients diagnosed with Multiple Sclerosis (MS) and a group of healthy control participants. These somatic tests were conducted both before and after a cognitive training intervention. The dataset enables the investigation of changes in somatic health indicators and physical well-being in response to cognitive training within these two distinct populations. This dataset provides valuable insights for researchers interested in somatic assessments, the potential benefits of cognitive training interventions on physical health, and the differences in somatic health outcomes between individuals with Multiple Sclerosis and healthy controls. It can inform holistic approaches to managing the well-being of MS patients.
DS09	Health	MS-NEUROPLAST_E	Patients with Multiple sclerosis, Healthy Controls, BrainHQ	This dataset provides information related to the usage of a cognitive training platform over a 3-month period by two groups: patients diagnosed with Multiple Sclerosis (MS) and a group of healthy control participants. It also includes detailed records of each participant's performance on cognitive training tasks administered through the platform. This dataset offers valuable insights for researchers interested in cognitive rehabilitation, cognitive training interventions, and the comparative analysis of cognitive performance between MS patients and healthy individuals. It can inform the development of targeted cognitive training programs for individuals with Multiple Sclerosis to enhance cognitive function and quality of life.

ID	Category	Name	Keywords	Description
DS10	Health	MS-NEUROPLAST_Φ	Patients with Multiple sclerosis, Healthy Controls, Fitbit	This dataset comprises comprehensive information regarding the 3-month monitoring of participants using wearable devices. The study includes two groups: patients diagnosed with Multiple Sclerosis (MS) and a group of healthy control participants. Data collected from the wearable devices provides insights into various aspects of participants' daily lives, including activity levels, sleep patterns, heart rate, and more. This dataset offers valuable insights for researchers interested in remote monitoring, daily activity assessments, and the impact of Multiple Sclerosis on the daily lives of patients. It can inform interventions and support strategies to improve the overall quality of life for individuals living with MS.
DS11	Health	INADVANCE	palliative care, end of life care	This dataset consists of questionnaire responses collected from 120 patients and 40 caregivers participating in a randomized control trial (RCT) aimed at monitoring individuals receiving palliative care compared to those who are not. The dataset includes questionnaire packages administered at four distinct time slots (initial, 6 weeks, 6 months, one year). The questionnaires cover a range of topics related to the patients' health, well-being, and caregiving experiences. This dataset provides valuable insights for researchers interested in palliative care interventions, patient-reported outcomes, and the dynamics of caregiving. It can inform the development of support strategies for patients and caregivers in palliative care settings and contribute to evidence-based practices in healthcare.

Table 2 Additional parameters for first exploration datasets

ID	Creation Date	Data Owner	GDPR status/consent	Anonymization Status	License	Language	Size (#entries)	Type
DOI1	2021	https://figshare.com/authors/Raoul Nuijten/9577289 (from TUE)	ERB approved	masked sensitive data, changed IDs	CC BY 4.0		50 users	CSV
DS01	2020	UPM		NO	CC BY 4.0	English/Spanish	~1000	CSV
DS02	2023	University of Stavanger	approved	anonymized	NA	English/Spanish	14 (23roducto 1-3); 13 (23roducto 4-6)	CSV
	2023	INTRAS	approved	anonymized	N/A	English/Spanish	20 older adults and 5 healthcare professionals	CSV
DOI2	2023	Laurea	Ethical evaluation approved	anonymized	CC BY 4.0	English	126	XLXS
DS04	2023	ThomasMore Mobilab&Care	approved	anonymized	N/A	English	1 subject performing multiple tasks; 35177 rows in CSV	CSV + video + raw files
DS05	2021	CAPTAIN Coach P.C.	approved	pending	N/A	English	698 rows	CSV + audio files
DS06	2021	Medical Phycis Laboratory & Digital Innovation, AUTH	approved	pending	N/A	English	MS: 120*2.700.000 rows 120*600.000 rows HC: 40*2.700.000 rows 40*600.000 rows	CSV

D12.1 Final interim report on Virtual Access

ID	Creation Date	Data Owner	GDPR status/consent	Anonymization Status	License	Language	Size (#entries)	Type
DS07	2021	Medical Phycis Laboratory & Digital Innovation, AUTH	approved	pending	N/A	English	MS: 120 rows HC: 40 rows	CSV
DS08	2021	Medical Phycis Laboratory & Digital Innovation, AUTH	approved	pending	N/A	English	MS: 120 rows HC: 40 rows	CSV
DS09	2021	Medical Phycis Laboratory & Digital Innovation, AUTH	approved	pending	N/A	English	~30000 rows	CSV
DS10	2021	Medical Phycis Laboratory & Digital Innovation, AUTH	approved	pending	N/A	English	~35*900 rows	CSV
DS11	2021	INADVANCE PC	approved	pseudonymized (each participant received a code)	IRAS No: 270472 ID ISRCTN24825698	English	Multiple	CSV

3.2.2 Increasing the quantity of datasets

The success of virtual access activities is influenced by the quality and diversity of datasets accessible to external researchers. Trying to increase the number of the available datasets, individual interviews were conducted with each VITALISE Research Infrastructure to encourage the discovery of additional valid datasets. The main aspects of the discussion covered a comprehensive review of the overall status of the VA, with a particular focus on the loaded NDM, along with the assessment of the datasets identified and those highlighted during the plenary meeting. The planning for the datasets review was initiated, to ensure conformance with the data model, along with the identification of potential datasets that may contribute to the objectives. More details can be found at the full template in Appendix A. Virtual Access 1:1 interview template.

As a result of this process, a total of 31 datasets have become available, categorized into VITALISE data model compliant, both anonymized and non-anonymized, and non-data model compliant. The distribution of these datasets is illustrated in the figure below.

Figure 1. Datasets per type of metadata

The content of the uploaded datasets can be categorized in the following:

- Device data,
- Demographic data,
- Questionnaire responses,
- Application usage,
- Health indicators (such as balance),
- Systems information (such as debug messages or logs),
- Direct project (such as Transnational Access) results,
- and meta-study data (e.g. participants responses to TA activities)

All Living Labs have contributed to VA catalogue with at least one dataset each.

3.3 Requirements for Virtual Access technical implementation

To ensure proper monitoring of the Virtual Access (VA) system, specific indicators and events occurring within the Discovery Portal were recorded automatically. Table 3 presents the requirements specification for the Discovery Portal, including the prioritization levels for its implementation so that it could be assessed from WP3.

Table 3. VA requirements for Discovery Portal

#	Requirement	Description	Priority
1	Terms and Conditions	When registering External Researchers (ER) must accept terms and conditions, which amongst common GDPR notifications should also highlight the need for users to be available to be contacted for answering a questionnaire and for publication derived from VA to acknowledge VITALISE project.	High
2	ER Registration validation	Each ER registration process must validate their email. The registration should include one of Researcher identification services (e.g. ORCID, WoS Researcher identifier, Research Gate). Social/federated login could also be interesting. This is so we can track publications of ER and monitor whether they are related to VITALISE datasets.	High
3	Contacting External Researchers	All registered ER must be reached in order to engage them to complete the satisfaction questionnaire. The preferred way is to extract the list of emails for mass email send, but the system may also provide the means of service notification system and the means to link to a page.	High
4	Log	<p>WP12 team must be able to access the log of the Discovery Portal, in concrete the log must contain the complete (since time of launch) registry of certain events. Each of these events should have at least the following properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timestamp (with at least minute resolution) • Event Type Identifier • User/LL id • Other relevant event type parameters <p>Event Types are specified in the next requirements.</p> <p>The log should be formatted in such a way that it must be easily processed automatically.</p>	High
5	Event Type: Registration	Whenever a new user has completed the verification process.	Medium
6	Event Type: Log In	Whenever a user logs into the system.	Medium
7	Event Type: Access	Whenever a user accesses a dataset, additional parameter: Dataset ref/id.	High
8	Event Type: Search	Whenever a user performs a search in the metadata catalogue, additional parameter: search term.	Low
9	Event Type: Data Set added	Whenever a LL registers a new Dataset to be used by ER. Param: dataset ref/id.	High

#	Requirement	Description	Priority
10	Event Type: Data Set updated	Whenever a LL updates a Dataset to be used by ER. Param: dataset ref/id.	High
11	Event Type: Remote Experiment run	Whenever a user launches a new Remote Experiment Run.	Medium
12	Event Type: Privacy Complaint	Whenever a user/LL issues a privacy concern. Param: complaint unique ID.	Low
13	Event Type: Privacy complain response	Whenever anyone answers to a privacy concern. Param: compliant unique ID.	Low
14	Event Type: Privacy Breach notification	Whenever a Breach notification is issued.	Low
15	Collecting some Statistics from the system	WP12 needs some overall statistics from the system. These can be provided through restricted Discovery Portal APIs or through other means such as dashboard, or file download in the admin panel. Following are some concrete statistics needed.	Medium
16	Statistics: Number of devices	Total number of (virtual) devices which contribute with datapoints to the overall datasets (from the ER point of view).	Low
17	Statistics: Number of connected LL	Total number of LL connected.	Medium
18	Statistics: Number of datasets	Total number of datasets available for VA.	High (if not provided by #9)
19	Statistics: Number of Types of accessible data	Total number of data models for which there are datapoints. For example number of device types which have data points available for VA.	Medium
20	Number of RAI ids generated	Total number of RAI ids generated.	Low

#	Requirement	Description	Priority
21	Access to RAI IDs	Number of accesses to RAI IDs, RAI finder function (potentially event with timestamp, client ID, RAI ID).	Low

These requirements were presented to WP3, and most were implemented into the Discovery Portal. Thus, the Discovery Portal provides crucial metrics for VA analysis.

VITALISE RAI Node

The RAI node is a software module that allows LLs managers to securely publish collected data in an on-premises approach. This module could be independently installed in any research infrastructure enabling researchers to make available datasets to the VITALISE ecosystem through a user-friendly interface, hosting them and their shareable data (anonymised or synthetic - so no real data ever leaves the RAI node) and communicating only metadata to the Discovery Portal. The VITALISE RAI Nodes facilitate the remote execution and registration of experiments by researchers through the Discovery Portal. Technical details about the RAI node specification and features can be found in Deliverable D3.2, while the deployment, installation and configuration can be found in Deliverable D3.6.

3.4 VITALISE Discovery Portal for Virtual Access

The Discovery Portal serves as the central gateway for Researchers to interact with the other modules of the service, establishing a direct communication with each deployed RAI Node. This module provides access to the metadata and datasets summary catalogue available within the VITALISE Ecosystem. The first step to access the VITALISE ecosystem as a Researcher is to register for gaining virtual access. The registration process is simple. Going to the Discovery Portal page (<https://vitalise-portal.iti.gr/>), and clicking the “Register” option, the Researcher should follow the required steps, providing affiliation and individual information, checking on the eligibility criteria, shortly describing their project and, finally, setting up a personal password.

Once the registration is confirmed, the Researcher can login, access the user profile and explore the Discovery Portal metadata catalogue. Researchers can identify, and then request, relevant shareable data versions of datasets stored within the LLs infrastructures for their studies, uncovering valuable insights and facilitating interdisciplinary collaboration. Once a dataset is identified as a target for an experiment, the DP allows the Researcher to schedule remote data analysis tasks on real datasets hosted in a selected RAI Node and then register results, if satisfactory, could be hashed and saved in a blockchain network.

More information about the Discovery Portal, its features, screenshots, and implementation details can be found in Deliverable D3.3. The requirements generated in Section 3.3 were addressed by the Discovery Portal developers in order to facilitate VA as described in this deliverable.

4 Data collection methodology

This section describes the methodological approach followed in defining and measuring variables for the VA evaluation. The metrics that have been selected collect user participation, system performance and quality of interaction during VITALISE VA.

Figure 2. VITALISE VA experiment data analysis

VA is evaluated by defining a set of hypotheses, which then need to be tested using evidence in the form of observed data. In this section we are formalising the data description, and how it is collected during the execution of VA. This data will be a combination of Quantitative values, arising from the usage of the tools; and Quantitative data which is collected through the application of questionnaires to VA participants.

4.1 Quantitative values

In order to measure indicators of VA success, the table below compiles the different metrics.

Please note that Table 3 and Table 4 contain shared resources, focusing primarily on events captured in the Discovery Portal. While the "Discovery Portal Requirements" table lists the required portal functionality and specifications, the "Quantitative Metrics to collect" table lists these captured data as important data points to assess the effectiveness and impact of the Virtual Access platform. It shows continuous growth and change.

Table 4. Quantitative Metrics to collect.

Metric	Description	Relation to VA
Event Type: Registration	Whenever a new user has completed the verification process	Keep track of registered users, after filtering invalid registrations, compute KPI1.2
Event Type: Log In	Whenever a user logs into the system	Keep track of user engagement, how often they come back to the platform? Map satisfaction questionnaire to actual usage.
Event Type: Search	Whenever a user performs a search in the metadata catalogue, additional parameter: search term	Analysing the engagement, contextualize KPI2.2, and gather feedback from the community as for what they are interested in and provide more of it.

Metric	Description	Relation to VA
Event Type: Dataset added	Whenever a LL registers a new Dataset to be used by VA participant.	Compute KPI2.1. Monitor the offering of Datasets. Contextualize other engagement metrics (e.g. is #Logins related to the total number of available datasets at that time?)
Event Type: Data Set updated	Whenever a LL updates a Dataset to be used by ER. Param: dataset ref/id	Monitor how often datasets are updated, contextualize KPI6.1.
Event Type: Remote Experiment run	Whenever a user launches a new Remote Experiment Run	Analysing the engagement, contextualize KPI5.2.
Event Type: Privacy Complaint	Whenever a user/LL issues a privacy concern. Param: complaint unique ID	Monitor GDPR issues with datasets, and Platform operations.
Event Type: Privacy complain response	Whenever anyone answers to a privacy concern. Param: compliant unique ID	Monitor GDPR issues with datasets, and Platform operations.
Event Type: Privacy Breach notification	Whenever a Breach notification is issued.	Monitor GDPR issues with datasets, Platform operations and quality.
Statistics: Number of devices	Total number of (virtual) devices which contribute with datapoints to the overall datasets	Compute KPI2.1.
Statistics: Number of connected LL	Total number of LL connected	Contextualize other metrics (such as #available Datasets), Compute KPI6.1.
Statistics: Number of datasets	Total number of datasets available for VA	Compute KPI2.1. Monitor the offering of Datasets.
Statistics: Number of Types of accessible data	Total number of data models for which there are datapoints. For example, number of device types which have data points available for VA.	Contextualize KPI2.1.
Number of RAI ids generated	Total number of RAI ids generated	Monitor supply-side.

Metric	Description	Relation to VA
Paper publication	Number of scientific publications from each VA participant derived from VA	Contextualize KPI2.2 and KPI5.2. Measure success of VA experience.

4.2 Qualitative values

To design the VA questionnaire, we researched several sources to ensure that the most applicable of those validated and within the scope were used. However, after several internal meetings the **Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)** and the **System Usability Scale (SUS)** were decided to be included as part of the VA final questionnaires. The TAM is applied for assessing user acceptance and how likely they are to use the technology while the SUS is highly specific to usability testing and provides a quick and user-friendly way to evaluate the usability aspects of a system.

4.2.1 Questionnaire Design

The present table describes the final shape of the VA questionnaire.

Table 5. VA questionnaire

VITALISE VA QUESTIONNAIRE		
Section	Item	Description
Demographics	Age range	[from 20 and under to 70 and above in 10-year non-overlapping intervals]
	Gender	[male, female, other]
	Education level	[options using ISCED 2011]
	Area of knowledge	[short open question]
System Usability Scale (SUS)	I think that I would like to use this system frequently.	1-5 likert scale
	I found the system unnecessarily complex.	1-5 likert scale
	I thought the system was easy to use.	1-5 likert scale
	I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system.	1-5 likert scale
	I found the various functions in this system were well integrated.	1-5 likert scale
	I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system.	1-5 likert scale
	I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly.	1-5 likert scale
	I found the system very cumbersome to use.	1-5 likert scale
	I felt very confident using the system.	1-5 likert scale
I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system.	1-5 likert scale	

VITALISE VA QUESTIONNAIRE		
Section	Item	Description
Evaluation VA	What kind of expectations did you have concerning your Virtual Access?	[Multi-line text]
	How well were your expectations regarding the Virtual Access met?	[Multi-line text]
	Please rate the data tool in terms of usefulness as it relates to your research process	1-5 likert scale
	What did you appreciate most about the Virtual Access?	[Multi-line text]
End-point	How likely are you to recommend the Vitalise Virtual Access to your colleagues or other researchers?	(0 not at all – 10 very likely) [options 0-10]
Report	Describe the context of your research (e.g., research project, PhD thesis, funding scheme, etc...)	[Multi-line text]
	Describe the objectives and expectation of VA in relation to your research (Objectives)	[Multi-line text]
	List the services/datasets you used during your VA (Data Sources)	[Multi-line text]
	Describe how you use these datasets, services, technologies and tools to carry out your research project (Methodology)	[Multi-line text]
	Describe the results achieved (List your Key Findings)	[Multi-line text]
	Are there any specific recommendations that VA should implement in relation to your research? (Recommendations)	[Multi-line text]
	How do you plan to disseminate the results of your research? (e.g., publications, articles, newsletters, LinkedIn...etc)	[Multi-line text]
	Will you allow open access of your generated data? If it is the case, how?	[Multi-line text]
	If it is the case, Do you intend to commercialize the research results? [optional]	[Multi-line text]
	Are there any future steps in your research where VA will play any role? [optional]	[Multi-line text]
	Any other conclusions to your experience with VA related to your research? [optional]	[Multi-line text]
	We would love to hear more feedback from you. Suggestions, comments, other experiences... help us to improve our service. [optional]	[Multi-line text]

5 Virtual Access experiment plan

The VA was executed in 3 phases: Preparatory, Execution and Analysis. In each phase all the previous tools, and methodologies, were used so that activities and decisions could be executed. Each of the phases is explained in the next subsections.

5.1 Preparatory phase

In order to prepare for VA there were some key activities that needed to be executed. Most notably was the preparation of the datasets catalogue to increase the supply to potential VA researchers, and ensuring the VITALISE platform was ready and functional to be used.

- Dataset curation: initial round of dataset identification and curation, with direct input by research infrastructures, WP12 provided a template based on what is described in section 3.2).
- Questionnaire definition: following the methodology described in section 4.2 in order to complete the experiment design.
- Metric Requirements: design and post the VITALISE metric requirements described in section 3.3 so they are implemented by the platform and quantitative data is collected to complete VA analysis.
- 1 on 1 interviews: an extra round of dataset identification and curation following the methodology described in section 2.1 guiding each research infrastructure through the process to expand the catalogue of available datasets as to improve the enrollment and engagement of VA researchers.
- Dissemination: Launch the VA open call, through all the mechanisms available to the project. WP13 reports directly on these activities. All dissemination activities link to the VA information portal (<https://vitalise-project.eu/virtual-access/>) which explains to VA candidates the goals of VA, the value, the overall experience, some samples of available datasets, as well as the steps to follow to enroll and get full access to the datasets.
- Testing the platform: ensure the system is stable enough to invite 3rd party participants, improve user experience, and therefore engagement. The result of this shows in different ways one of which is the enhancement of information for the VA participant not only throughout the recruitment and registration process, but also as part of the Discovery Portal tool itself.

The preparatory phase lasted about 7 months (from M26 to M31), before the launch of VA through the dissemination campaigns.

5.2 Execution phase

Once the VA has been launched, a set of continuous activities were being executed to ensure the VA experience is running smoothly and the KPIs were being collected. These activities included:

- Monitoring user registration
- Monitoring technical issues
- Monitoring experiment runs
- Monitoring publications
- Contacting VA participants

The execution phase run for 6 months, intensifying towards the end of the project.

5.3 Analysis phase

Once all the data had been collected the analysis phase started. In this phase the data analysis produced the final VA experience report, presented in D12.2 - Report from VITALISE platform access and usage; where the results are reported.

6 Reports produced by researchers on VA registration

Upon registration, users are requested to fill in a form describing their organization, as well as agreeing with terms and conditions for VA (like the requirement to mention VITALISE for any derivative works). The registration allows to register up to 5 members per team. We filtered the results removing any team which was clearly invalid, namely testing users. There is a total of 139 valid teams registered.

Analysing this questionnaire, we find that the distribution of “research background” (one of the questions asked) is biased towards Academic researcher, as see in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Distribution of research background

As for the distribution of countries of origin of the registered Organization, there is a high number of participants from Spain and Greece, which is probably a reflection of the VITALISE consortium and its network. Figure 4 represents the results from European countries, there are 3 more registries from North American Countries.

Figure 4 Number of Registered Teams per Country. Canada accounts for 2 more Cyprus, and USA for another one each

The final question on the registration form is an open text field where VA participants are asked to describe their research project. Applying our own method (described in section 2.1.1) there are some aggregated ways to analyse this data. For example, word count distribution as seen in Figure 5, with a mean of 36 words per project description.

Figure 5 Word Count distribution for project description by VA participants

A word cloud could help us visualize the general intent in the descriptions. Figure 6 represents the generated word cloud. Words like “project” “Research” and “data/datasets” are prominent in the descriptions, which align with VA objectives and dissemination activities of VA. Interesting words like “health”, “technologies” and “management” are also present.

Figure 6 Word cloud of project description by VA participants. Using tagcrowd.com tool

The following are categories of projects sorted by the number of matching descriptions:

- **Research and Academic Work:** Includes various academic research projects, studies, and thesis work across different fields such as healthcare, technology, aging, neuroscience, biomechanics, and more.
- **Healthcare and Medical Applications:** Projects related to healthcare, medical technology, patient care, disease management, rehabilitation, and medical imaging.
- **Data Analysis and Machine Learning:** Projects focusing on data analysis, machine learning, artificial intelligence, and the development of algorithms for healthcare applications.

- **Technology Development and Implementation:** Projects involving the development and implementation of technology solutions, software applications, digital biomarkers, virtual reality, IoT, and cybersecurity.
- **Education and Training:** Projects centred around education, training, and pedagogical programs related to healthcare, technology, and digital literacy.
- **Living Labs and Innovation Hubs:** Initiatives aiming to create collaboration hubs, living labs, or innovation centres focused on interdisciplinary research, co-creation, and societal impact.
- **Digital Transformation and Smart Solutions:** Projects addressing digital transformation, smart solutions, and the integration of new technologies in various sectors such as water management, cultural industries, and healthcare.
- **Synthetic Data Generation and Privacy Protection:** Projects focused on synthetic data generation, privacy protection, and the development of secure systems for data sharing and analysis in healthcare.
- **Project Management and Coordination:** Involves roles related to project management, coordination, and leadership in software projects, healthcare initiatives, and research programs.
- **Test and Evaluation:** Projects involving testing, evaluation, validation, and optimization of systems, algorithms, and technologies for various applications in healthcare and beyond.

The following are some identified needs from these project descriptions, sorted by the number of applicable descriptions:

- **Access to Comprehensive Datasets:** Many researchers express a need for access to datasets provided by projects like VITALISE to support their research inquiries. They seek diverse datasets covering various aspects of health, technology, and social sciences.
- **Advanced Analytical Tools and ICT Infrastructure:** Researchers require access to robust ICT tools and e-infrastructures to facilitate data curation, analysis, and interpretation. They aim to leverage advanced analytical techniques, including machine learning algorithms, deep learning models, and statistical analysis methods.
- **Interdisciplinary Research Opportunities:** Researchers are interested in exploring interdisciplinary connections between fields such as healthcare, technology, psychology, neuroscience, and environmental science. They seek opportunities to collaborate across disciplines to address complex research questions.
- **Validation of Hypotheses and Models:** Researchers aim to use datasets to validate hypotheses, test new algorithms, and develop machine learning models. They need access to high-quality data to assess the performance and accuracy of their models in various domains, including healthcare, aging, and environmental monitoring.
- **Enhanced Patient Care and Treatment Outcomes:** Projects focus on leveraging data-driven insights to improve patient care, enhance treatment outcomes, and inform healthcare policies. Researchers aim to identify patterns, trends, and innovative solutions that can contribute to better healthcare delivery and management.
- **Technology Adoption and Innovation:** Researchers are interested in studying technology adoption rates among different demographics, including older adults, patients with chronic conditions, and diverse cultural groups. They seek to develop user-centred technological solutions that can enhance quality of life and promote digital inclusion.
- **Addressing Societal Challenges and Public Health Issues:** Projects aim to address societal challenges such as obesity, mental health disorders, aging populations, and environmental sustainability. Researchers seek to develop holistic solutions, preventive interventions, and policy recommendations to mitigate these challenges and improve public health outcomes.

7 Conclusions

This deliverable describes the Virtual Access (VA) experience design and methods. It includes cataloguing datasets with all the necessary considerations for publishing the datasets to the open science community, in full conformance with regulatory landscape as well as the proper licensing for viable exploitation of the published datasets. These methods could also be used to design future experiments and extract as much valuable information as possible from the same process. There were other specific licensing schemes for datasets found, which may be used in other instances of VA, like Open Data Commons Public Domain Dedication and License with some legal language to formally dedicate the data to the public domain; and Open Data Commons Open Database License which allows others to share, modify, and use the dataset for any purpose, as long as they attribute the original creator and share any derivative works under the same license. License considerations were initially formulated within the scope of the VISTALISE project, reflecting the project's time constraints and objectives. However, when considering longer timeframes, sustainability, and dataset exploitation, additional factors such as commercialization of datasets and definition of new licensing models and terms come into play.

This deliverable reports on the information collected during the registration of the external researchers, particularly on the declared organizations, and the description of the project for which the VA will be used. This report shows that most of the participants are academic researchers, although there is also a healthy spread of students and private sector participants. Most of the declared organizations are from either Spain or Greece; Belgium and Italy in 3rd and 4th place, with most of the representation across Europe as well as some from North America. Within the descriptions of the dataset usage scope, we can find high interest in datasets and research in general, but it is also interesting that health and technology play a substantial aspect of the redescribed projects. Most participants declared the VA to be used for research and education, there is also mentions of the Living lab, digital transformation and synthetic data generation. From the descriptions, common identified needs are the access to datasets and analytical tools to analyse this data, both of which are covered by the VITALISE VA platform. In general, it seems that the execution phase has been successful in recruiting the targeted profile of participants, with an excellent spread of locations, backgrounds, and interests.

Some of the limitation of the VA implementation included the limited time for disseminating the VA call and accessing the data. The actual realization of the VA procedures took place during the last 3 months of the project due to the technology maturity level which reached a well functional system some months before the project ending. In addition, any information related to the reporting of the researchers relies on the information collected during the registration of the external researchers. This is due to the fact that the external researchers were not obliged to report back to the consortium after benefit of the VA access as this could have been an inhibitory factor for their participation. This is a lesson learnt from the TA where the 10-page length of the application that was used in the 1st call led to only few applications being submitted.

Overall, the effectiveness of the virtual access activities is tied not only to the quality and diversity but also to the availability and appropriateness of the data provided to external researchers. The implemented dataset archiving can be further enhanced by improving collaboration and feedback mechanisms between data providers and researchers, leading to robust analysis and insights through continuous expansion and refinement of datasets.

Appendix

Appendix A. Virtual Access 1:1 interview template

Review General VA Status (uploaded NDMs)

Review Identified Datasets

Reviewing identified datasets from the Plenary meeting

Review Plan for Data Model Compliant Datasets

- What?
- When?
- Where?
- how?

Identify Possible Datasets

One way to identify data is to review the possible media (and format) the data may be in:

- File tables, in formats such as CSV or Excel.
- Relational Databases, typically compatible with the SQL (Structured Query Language), and there are many dialects, which correspond with the different database management implementation, such as MySQL, Postgres, MariaDB, SQLite.
- Non-Relational Databases, these are a broad category of data management paradigms which do not rely on tables and relations between them. Table 6-1 shows some examples by types.
- API endpoints, modern applications have APIs for interoperability, these APIs may be REST (Representational State Transfer) which often offer JSON (Java Script Object Notation) representations of data. Older APIs may be based on XML (eXtensible Markup Language) using formal protocols such as SOAP (Simple Object Access Protocol).
- Standardised formats, there are many formats for many purposes, but in accordance with the presented ontology there are a couple of very relevant standards.
 - FHIR (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources) is the emerging standard for health care, so many modern systems may find they use this standard for data exchange,
 - CAD file for things like floorplans;
 - There are also many image and video formats, however, and in anticipation of the next phase, we are not going to list them.
- General files (such as Word, PDF documents or Power Point presentations) and webpages, most of this media is intended for human consumption exclusively, which means that automatizing the information extraction from these sources is challenging; to denote this type of data is labeled as unstructured data. There are types of data to be extracted:
 - Generic content analysis (wordcloud, NLP, topic analysis, word count, etc)
 - Metadata analysis (topics, keywords, file names, etc.)
 - Content analysis (tables, and data contained it them)

- Semantic formats (RDF, JSON-LD), in this case the data is already semantic.

Dataset Candidate	Table	Relational Data Base	Non-Relational	API	Standard format	General Files	Semantic Format

Another procedure to identify potential sources of data is to analyse the domains, or the logical categories, of the information.

Data Valuation

Deciding which of these is valuable enough for continuing the process. As there may be many datasets, a cost-benefit analysis must be performed at this stage. Additionally, the system performance when data is harmonized could be hindered if many data sources are connected. Thus, the importance of filtering the relevant information sources.

The criteria to apply are:

- Is the information relevant?
- Is the information representable?
- Is the information available?
- Licencing considerations
- Volume of the information.
- Quality of the information. Consider if the data to be shared provides from reliable sources, and if the dataset is consistent. For example, data providing from wearable devices may be abundant, but it needs to be considered if the data points are guaranteed to be from the said user, and in the specified conditions; or datasets that are manually collected consider the possibility of errors in transcription which affect the dataset quality.
- Transformation costs: Identifying tabulable data.
- Privacy and legal considerations, ensuring for example GDPR rights and regulations are followed and maintained when collecting the data.

Data-set	Relevance	Representation	Availability	Licensing	Volume	Quality	Costs	Privacy and Legal (GDPR)